

Technical Report

A unified lexicon of predictive DNA sequence motifs from ENCODE transcription factor binding and chromatin accessibility assays

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Abstract

Regulatory DNA sequences encode motif lexicons and syntax that govern transcription factor (TF) binding and chromatin accessibility, determining when and where genes are expressed. Most current motif compendia are based on traditional statistical enrichment-based motif discovery methods applied to TF binding assays. Here, we present one of the first comprehensive compendia of predictive motifs derived from deep learning models of regulatory DNA trained systematically across thousands of ENCODE TF binding and chromatin accessibility datasets. We trained BPNet and ChromBPNet models on 2,638 TF ChIP-seq datasets (867 TFs) and 1,512 chromatin accessibility datasets (440 cell types), extracting 95,552 sequence motifs that quantitatively predict base-resolution regulatory profiles. To consolidate these motifs into a unified regulatory lexicon, we developed MotifCompendium, a Python package which features a GPU-accelerated motif similarity calculation, similarity-based motif clustering, filters for removing noisy, uninformative motifs, and other utilities to facilitate motif analyses. MotifCompendium can compute the pairwise similarity of 10,000 motifs in 6 seconds on a 12GB GPU. Using MotifCompendium, we consolidated the learned motifs across all models into 1,921 unique TF binding motifs and 1,762 chromatin accessibility motifs. Our motifs show substantial overlap with existing databases (explaining 93% of known TF binding motifs in curated motif databases), while 20% represent entirely novel binding modes, not captured through traditional motif discovery approaches. We identify previously uncharacterized zinc finger-like motifs, composite elements with spacing preferences, and cell-type-specific regulatory variants. We also show that TF binding motifs and chromatin accessibility motifs remain highly orthogonal, that only share a ~13% overlap. This work provides both a foundational resource of predictive models, a

unified model-derived regulatory motif lexicon and a scalable computational framework for extracting sequence features that drive quantitative regulatory function.

Introduction

Transcriptional regulation serves a major role of the noncoding genome, determining the level of transcription of nearby genes that, in turn, are expressed into cellular biological function^{1,2}. Mapping noncoding *cis*-regulatory elements (cREs) has identified transcription factor (TFs) and their binding sites ('motifs') as key drivers of transcriptional regulation, with TFs binding to specific, high-affinity DNA sequences, that further activate or inhibit nearby transcriptional machinery³. However, while these high-affinity DNA sequences are abundant in the genome, TFs selectively occupy only a small fraction of potential sites, governed by cellular context, such as direct concentration of TFs, and indirect cooperation and competition with other TFs and nucleosomes⁴⁻⁶.

Most current motif compendia, including widely-used databases such as JASPAR²⁸, HOCOMOCO²⁹, and CIS-BP³⁰, are based on traditional statistical enrichment-based motif discovery methods applied to *in vitro* and *in vivo* TF binding assays. Recent advances in deep learning have demonstrated that sequence-to-function models can learn more accurate sequence models of TF binding and chromatin accessibility. Interpretation frameworks enable discovery of predictive motifs and syntax from these models. For example, BPNet, trained on base-resolution TF binding profiles from ChIP-nexus and ChIP-seq data, has been shown to learn predictive binding motifs and syntax¹⁶. Similarly, ChromBPNet, trained on DNase-seq and ATAC-seq profiles, has shown to learn the underlying binding sites of cell type-specific TFs, while isolating enzymatic bias¹⁷. However, so far, deep learning models have been applied to select experiments, at individual scale. In order to gain a comprehensive understanding of the regulatory landscape, we would need an extensive expansion of identifying the regulatory motifs and syntax.

To map the dynamic, highly variable regulatory landscape, the ENCODE Project has continued to map the genome^{7,8}, expanding the annotation of regulatory elements in ENCODE 4, by creating an extensive database of transcriptional regulatory readouts, including TF chromatin immunoprecipitation sequencing (TF ChIP-seq), to identify direct TF binding sites⁹, and DNase I hypersensitive sites sequencing (DNase-seq) and Assay for Transposase-Accessible Chromatin using sequencing (ATAC-seq), to identify accessible euchromatin in different cell type and cell states^{10,11}.

However, even given experimental readouts, computational methods are required to map and identify specific TF binding sites, and traditional methods have often resulted in several shortcomings, including low statistical representation, particularly for extended sequences that capture motif syntax, confounding by repeat elements such as in transposable elements (TEs), and even direct enzymatic bias in the assays (from DNase I nuclease and Tn5 transposase)^{12–15}.

In this work, we expand the analysis across the entire ENCODE 4 dataset of TF ChIP-seq, DNase-seq, and ATAC-seq, at production scale. To manage the unprecedented scale of learned sequence features, we develop MotifCompendium: a GPU-accelerated Python package to compare, combine, and manage sequence motifs from deep learning models, at scale. We share the final unique, non-redundant set of sequence motifs as a preliminary dictionary for the language and syntax of human transcriptional regulation. Whereas existing motif databases contain motifs derived from sequence-enrichment methods applied to TF-binding assay readouts, our work is the first large-scale effort to unify deep learning-derived motifs of both direct TF binding and chromatin accessibility.

Results

Deep learning models trained on ENCODE data recapitulate diversity of regulatory function

The ENCODE project has performed extensive functional profiling of the human regulatory genome by producing thousands of functional characterizations of the human genome across diverse cellular contexts. Among the data produced are 2,638 TF ChIP-seq datasets targeting 867 TFs and 1,775 ATAC-seq and DNASE-seq datasets performed in 440 unique bulk tissue contexts.

We trained sequence-to-function deep learning models on each of these datasets. In particular, we trained BpNet models¹⁶ on each TF ChIP-seq dataset and ChromBpNet models¹⁷ on each of the ATAC-seq and DNASE-seq datasets. BpNet and ChromBpNet are both convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that predict base-resolution signal in 1kb regions as a function of the local (2,114 bp) regulatory sequence context; for both, predictions are made using two heads: a *counts head*, which predicts the total sequence read over the region, and a *profile head*, which predicts the distribution of that sequence read over bases and positions. For BpNet models, signal is measured as stranded 5'-end read coverage profiles, whereas for ChromBpNet models, signal is measured as strand-agnostic Tn5 or DNASE insertion coverage. Both architectures explicitly model assay bias, with ChromBpNet featuring a submodule which is

independently trained to learn enzyme bias, and can be *factorized*, or excised from the full architecture, to produce *bias-corrected* predictions.

For each dataset, a set of training regions was defined using a combination of dataset-derived peaks and G/C content-matched nonpeak regions. Models were trained per dataset using a 5-fold chromosome-wise cross-validation scheme, with each fold containing all training regions in a subset of chromosomes. Typically, a single assay-specific bias model can be used across multiple ATAC or DNase-seq datasets for ChromBPNet bias correction due to the overall similarity among datasets of the signal corresponding to DNase or Tn5 enzymatic bias, respectively. However, in DNase-seq data in particular, bias correction with a non-dataset specific bias model may fail, which is characterized by the presence of a DNase in the list of discovered motifs following model interpretation; an abundance of low-complexity motifs in the list of discovered motifs; or both. In such circumstances, we trained a dataset-specific bias model, using the same nonpeak regions as those in the corresponding ChromBPNet model. Approximately 3% of the DNase datasets that we set out to train failed this custom bias model procedure, and these consisted almost entirely of low-quality data. Each model's performance was evaluated on the peaks of per-fold held-out test chromosomes. Evaluations included checking counts prediction correlations, computing Jensen Shannon Divergences (JSDs) on profile predictions, and auROC for the model being able to distinguish peak and nonpeak regions.

All of the models, training data, predictions, and bias-corrected predictions on dataset-derived peaks and all ENCODE cCREs⁸ have been uploaded to the ENCODE portal¹⁸ for public access. The data integrity of all the models and complementary data were systematically verified by confirming that the downloaded versions of all the files exactly matched the on-hand versions we produced.

Systematic model interpretation allows discovery of atlas-scale *in vivo* regulatory sequence elements

Next, we performed a well-established, systematic interpretation of the models to understand the sequence features predicted to drive assay readout for each dataset.

First, we used DeepLIFT/DeepSHAP¹⁹, an algorithm for interpreting deep learning models, by calculating the contribution of each input feature towards the model's final predicted output, to calculate the contribution of each of base towards the model's predicted total counts and profile shape for a given peak region. For contribution scores towards counts predictions, scores can be interpreted as each base's contribution towards the total predicted assay signal in the region, while for contribution scores towards profile shapes, scores can be interpreted as each base's contribution towards

the total log probability of the profile shape. For the ChromBPNet models, contributions were computed using the bias-factorized models. To compute a consensus score per dataset, the contribution score of all 5-fold models were averaged.

Next, we used TF-MoDISco²⁰, a motif discovery algorithm for extracting key contiguous sequence features in deep learning contribution scores in the form of contribution weight matrices (CWMs), to identify motifs that the models repeatedly rely on for predicting assay readout. TF-MoDISco was run on both the counts DeepLIFT contribution scores and profile DeepLIFT contributions scores separately, per dataset.

Lastly, we used FiNeMo²¹, a GPU-accelerated motif hit caller for identifying occurrences of TF-MoDISco motifs within deep learning model contribution scores, to identify genomic instances of the identified motifs. FiNeMo was run on both the counts TF-MoDISco motifs on the counts DeepLIFT contribution scores that they were discovered from, and the profile TF-MoDISco motifs on the profile DeepLIFT contributions scores that were discovered from, per dataset.

For each dataset, the average counts and profile DeepLIFT contribution scores, the counts and profile TF-MoDISco CWM motifs, and FiNeMo motif instances have been uploaded to the ENCODE portal for public access¹⁸.

MotifCompendium provides a scalable, flexible, and comprehensive framework for motif analysis

With an extensive set of key regulatory elements in the form of CWM motifs, across numerous TFs and cell types, we needed a tractable method to analyze and coalesce the set. One problem, for example, is that many of these motifs repeatedly appear across multiple datasets, most obviously in the case of biological replicates. To solve this, we sought to collapse the TF-MoDISco-derived motifs into a non-redundant set, to determine the true number of unique motifs driving regulatory function across the ENCODE datasets.

While many established tools compute motif similarity or cluster motifs, no existing software had the capabilities or tractability required for this task. First, we needed to perform motif clustering at a scale that we found to be computationally intractable for many established tools. Also, we needed to cluster CWMs, which can contain both positive and negative values, and are incompatible with existing software that are designed to work with non-negative position frequency matrices (PFMs) or position weight matrices (PWMs). And crucially, because we are not working with a curated set of motifs, we needed a principled solution for filtering out motifs that were noisy, uninformative, or did not represent transcription factor binding motifs, like repeats.

Figure 1. A. Overview of BPNNet-style model architecture. **B.** ENCODE deep learning model pipeline for TF ChIP-seq, DNase-seq, and ATAC-seq datasets.

Here, we introduce MotifCompendium²², a Python package designed to enable rapid and scalable motif clustering and to provide a comprehensive framework for organizing and analyzing motifs. Addressing the needs for performing ENCODE-scale motif analysis, MotifCompendium is natively compatible with both CWMs and PFMs/PWMs, provides utilities to automatically flag and filter noisy or uninformative motifs, implements automated motif annotation with composite motif labeling, and features intuitive and informative visualization formats. In addition, MotifCompendium adopts an object-oriented design strategy, allowing for flexible biologically driven analyses and simplified loading, storing, and sharing of data.

At the core of the MotifCompendium package is an algorithm for computing the similarity between any pair of motifs. The similarity score that the algorithm computes is a measure of motif similarity we introduce in this work. The similarity between two motifs is defined as the maximum similarity across all possible alignments of the motifs, and the similarity at any particular alignment can be thought of as a cosine similarity over aligned bases (Figure 2a). The similarity measure is symmetric, ensuring that the similarity between two motifs is the same regardless of the order in which they are considered. The similarity measure is also bound between 0 and 1, with a similarity of 1 only being achieved for identical motifs.

Given two sets of motifs, the similarity algorithm simultaneously computes the similarity and optimal alignment between all cross-set pairs of motifs. The algorithm is implemented as a numerical algorithm consisting entirely of tensor arithmetic, naturally enabling GPU acceleration (Figure 2b). A meta-algorithm breaks large similarity calculations into smaller chunks to limit the total memory usage, which allows for similarity to be computed on massive sets of motifs with limited on-GPU memory. The symmetry properties of the similarity score and alignment are also leveraged to skip redundant calculations. Using a 12 GB Titan V GPU, the MotifCompendium similarity algorithm computes pairwise similarity and optimal alignments for 10,000 motifs (50 million pairs) in 6 seconds, in our benchmarks against existing motif-similarity tools, was faster than all other approaches (Figure 2c).

MotifCompendium makes two key choices regarding CWM representation and processing which improve the quality of similarity scores. First, to distinguish positive and negative motifs and treat negative motifs as having no similarity with positive motifs as opposed to having negative similarity, MotifCompendium uses a novel *8-channel* motif representation for CWMs. Traditionally, motifs are represented as matrices with one dimension representing the length of the motif and the other dimension representing the possible bases at each position: A, C, G, and T. This standard *4-channel* representation features one channel per base, whereas the 8-channel motif representation has a separate positive and negative channel for each base: A+, A-, C+, C-, G-, G+, T-, T+ (this particular ordering was chosen so that reverse complements could be computed by reversing the order of the base channels) (Figure 2d). 8-channel representations have the added constraint that at each position, the positive and negative channels of any base cannot both be non-zero.

Second, when processing CWMs, MotifCompendium also implements an optional per-position information content scaling. When comparing the similarity between IC-scaled CWMs to the similarity between their non-IC-scaled counterparts, we found that contribution scores became more consistent because uninformative high-entropy flanking regions were effectively down-weighted.

We benchmarked the quality of our similarity scores by comparing our scores to those produced by Tomtom^{23, 24}, one of the most well-established and longstanding motif similarity algorithms (Figure 2e). We computed the pairwise similarity between all 6,302 motifs published in the Human Development Multiomic Atlas²⁵ (HDMA) using both methods. All motifs had a MotifCompendium self-similarity of 1 and a Tomtom self-similarity p-value of 1e-15. Next, we identified all other motif pairs that were scored as being identical (MotifCompendium similarity > 0.999 or Tomtom p-value <= 1e-15) by either method. Visually, we found that motif pairs that MotifCompendium scored as being identical looked much more identical than those that Tomtom scored as being

identical. Next, we scanned through MotifCompendium similarity scores from 0 to 1 and identified the median corresponding Tomtom similarity p-value in order to identify a correspondence between the two scores. We then systematically considered all motif pairs which had the same similarity score with respect to one of the methods, and characterized the variance in similarity scores given by the other method. Motif pairs at MotifCompendium's 0.95 threshold seem to have consistent levels of dissimilarity, whereas motif pairs at Tomtom's corresponding $1e-9$ p-value had more variance in their levels of visual dissimilarity, with some pairs being near identical and other pairs having different consensus sequences altogether. These inspections suggested that MotifCompendium's similarity measure respected both sequence and contribution and could be meaningful for downstream similarity-based motif clustering.

The MotifCompendium framework also includes downstream similarity-based clustering methods. A user-provided similarity threshold is applied against a motif similarity matrix to produce an adjacency matrix of a graph over the motifs, with two motifs having an edge if their similarity is higher than the specified similarity threshold. Then, a graph clustering or community detection algorithm like the Leiden algorithm^{26, 27} is applied to the motif graph (Figure 2f).

To further benchmark the similarity measure, we clustered both the MotifCompendium-derived similarity matrix and the Tomtom-derived similarity matrix of the (HDMA) motifs using Leiden clustering at corresponding similarity thresholds. We measured the concordance of the resultant clusterings with the ground-truth clustering provided in the original atlas (Figure 2g). Both the adjusted Rand index (ARI) and adjusted mutual information score (AMI) of clustering with MotifCompendium's similarity scores track closely alongside the corresponding scores when clustering with Tomtom's similarity scores, suggesting that MotifCompendium similarity scores are of comparable quality to the well-established Tomtom similarity scores.

MotifCompendium additionally offers more advanced clustering options and utilities, including a hierarchical clustering scheme built on top of the similarity-based clustering, which enables performing tasks like only clustering motifs within tissue types or clustering clusters of motifs. Built in quality control metrics help users identify appropriate clustering similarity thresholds and automatically detect and correct clustering errors.

MotifCompendium defines several metrics of motif informativeness that are used to flag and filter uninformative or noisy motifs. The *full motif entropy* metric can identify motifs which are single base peaks. The full motif entropy, *weighted base entropy*, and *weighted position entropy* metrics can identify noisy motifs with little consensus. The *copair entropy* and *copair composition* can help identify single-base repeats. And the

dinucleotide entropy, *dinucleotide alternating composition*, and *dinucleotide score*, can all identify alternating bases, and are particularly helpful for flagging motifs which are actually just high G/C-content sequences.

Within the MotifCompendium package is the titular MotifCompendium object, which serves as the primary abstraction for motif analyses. Compendia can be constructed directly from TF-MoDISco output files or from common MEME-format PFM databases. When a compendium is constructed, similarity and alignment calculations are implicitly performed. The object maintains an associated user-editable, per-motif metadata. This metadata can be used to easily subset or slice the compendium, facilitating downstream analyses. Compendia can easily be loaded and saved in a compressed file format that preserves motifs, alignments, similarity results, metadata, and clustering state (Figure 2h).

Compendia can have their constituent motifs automatically label and annotate motifs based on a reference set of motifs. Reference motifs can either come from traditional PFM databases like those downloadable from JASPAR²⁸ and HOCOMOCO²⁹, or from previously annotated MotifCompendium objects, enabling straightforward transfer and sharing of annotations across projects. The motif annotation algorithm can detect composite motifs by recognizing multiple supported cores within a pattern and assigning multi-label annotations when appropriate, making routine annotation of motif composites possible.

Compendia can be visualized in a collection view that leverages stored motif alignments to display and compare sets of similar motifs in a coherent, interpretable layout. Compendia can also be visualized as an interactable, editable, and filterable spreadsheet-like tables of motifs and their metadata. Both views produce standalone HTML files that can be viewed in any internet browser and easily shared with others.

Figure 2. A. MotifCompendium’s notion of similarity as being the maximum similarity over all possible alignments. **B.** A schematic of MotifCompendium’s similarity algorithm. First, a stack of motifs is split per base and tiled into two tensors. Then, a batched matrix multiply is performed per-base to give per-base similarity subscores. The similarity subscores are then added across all bases. This gives the pairwise similarity across all shifted alignments. This is done for the reverse complement pair, as well, to find the best possible alignment. **C.** A log/log-scale plot of the speed to compute the pairwise similarity between a set of motifs. MotifCompendium is multiple orders of magnitude faster than any other benchmarked solution. **D.** A depiction of MotifCompendium’s 8-channel motif representation. **E.** A comparison between MotifCompendium and Tomtom similarity scores. **F.** A schematic of how similarity-based motif clustering is done in MotifCompendium. **G.** The ARI and AMI of clustering using Tomtom’s vs MotifCompendium’s similarity matrix at a series of corresponding similarity thresholds. ARI and AMI track very closely, indicating similar levels of agreement with the ground truth. **H.** A schematic of the MotifCompendium object structure.

MotifCompendium enables processing, reconciliation, and analysis of ENCODE motifs

With MotifCompendium, we could begin to analyze the ENCODE model interpretations at scale. First, in order to select our starting motifs, we manually selected datasets and models with strong performance and highly reliable motifs. For BpNet models, we manually selected for models that discovered a known motif of the ChIP target TF was identified by comparing with publicly available motifs from JASPAR 2024 Core²⁸, HOCOMOCO V13²⁹, CIS-BP V3³⁰, zinc finger bacterial one-hybrid (B1H) system^{31, 32}. Except for the ZNF models, which generally result in lower model performance, all models were also filtered for having greater than a median 0.5 Pearson correlation coefficient for the counts head across the model folds. For ChromBpNet models, we manually selected for models that discovered known TF binding motifs, while not exhibiting the motif of the enzyme (representing the enzyme's sequence bias) or GC/AT rich motifs (representing experimental GC/AT bias). Additionally, given the ease of interpretability of counts contribution scores—namely, that each base's contribution towards the total predicted assay signal in the region—we selected the counts motifs only during this analysis. This resulted in a set of 1,644 high-quality BpNet models, across 464 TFs, with 19,739 discovered motifs, and a set of 1,512 high-quality ChromBpNet models, across 440 cell types, with 75,813 motifs. We used MotifCompendium to consolidate each set of TF and chromatin accessibility motifs down to their respective unique, non-redundant sets.

ENCODE TF Motif Compendium: Consolidated ENCODE TF ChIP-seq BpNet-derived motifs

When consolidating TF ChIP-seq BpNet-derived motifs, there were several dataset specific considerations to take into account. First, the ENCODE Project contains ChIP-seq dataset for the same TF across different cell types, as well as direct biological replicates. Second, not all TF ChIP-derived motifs are the binding motifs of the targeted TF; in fact, many are motifs of a partner TF, that cooperatively interacts with the target TF. And third, TFs can have similar binding motifs, particularly within sequence families, but even outside of lineage; in other words, for a given motif pattern, there are often more than one possible TF that is responsible for the binding pattern. We used MotifCompendium to resolve these issues, while collapsing motifs into a unique, non-redundant set.

First, we divided the motifs per target TF (agnostic of cell type), and cross-referenced each motif to a set of the target TF's known *in vitro*-derived motifs from publicly available TF motif databases: JASPAR 2024 Core²⁸, HOCOMOCO V13²⁹, CIS-BP V3³⁰, Codebook³³, and CAP-SELEX³⁴. Motifs that matched with a known, *in vitro*-confirmed

motif with a similarity greater than 0.88 were identified as 'direct', and motifs that did not match were identified as 'indirect'. This ensured that all 'direct' motifs have a known, orthogonally validated motif, derived from an *in vitro* setting (without any other cooperative proteins) and were ensured to be a direct binding mode of the target TF (or paralog), and not of any other cooperative TF. In contrast, 'indirect' motifs were identified from the target TF's ChIP-seq, however, had no orthogonal *in vitro* evidence of binding in this affinity pattern, and hence may or may not be the result of direct binding by the target TF. For indirect motifs, we additionally filtered out for low complexity motifs, including tandem repeats and GC/AT bias. This created a starting set of 2,816 direct motifs and 9,077 indirect motifs, organized per TF.

Next, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motifs that describe each TF's direct and indirect binding modes, we performed a first round of clustering of motifs per TF, per direct/indirect categorization, by applying first, Leiden algorithm^{26, 27} recursively with a Constant Potts Model metric on the similarity matrix thresholded at 0.88 to converge to a stable, coarse round of clustering, followed by applying a Densely Connected Components algorithm³⁵ on the similarity matrix thresholded at 0.92 to ensure that any clusters, when represented as the average of its constituents, could not create another higher order cluster where all its constituents have a similarity greater than 0.92. This resulted in 755 unique direct binding clusters (labeled as '{TF}_{#}'), and 5,137 unvalidated, indirect binding clusters (labeled as '{TF}_X_{#}') across 464 TFs. Each cluster was averaged over its constituent motifs to construct a single representative motif per cluster.

Lastly, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motif patterns that are generally observable from ChIP-seq, agnostic of target TF (or in other words, all major observable ChIP-seq motif patterns), we performed a second round of clustering on the 755 direct and 5,137 indirect cluster motifs. The clustering method was the same as in the first round. This resulted in 1,921 unique, general ChIP-seq-derived motif patterns in total. We refer to this final set as the 'ENCODE TF Motif Compendium'. In order to keep track of all possible TFs that could potentially be directly binding to the motifs, we took three approaches to labeling: for the simplest case, where the motif pattern contains one or more direct motifs as its constituents, we labeled the identity of all the direct motifs' target TFs as the possible binding TFs of the motif pattern. For motif patterns that do not have any direct motifs as its constituents, we separately clustered known motifs from multiple highly curated, external TF motif databases, whose motif-to-TF mapping was consequently known, into 888 unique motif patterns, and created a mapping of each major motif pattern to all its constituent motifs' TFs (called 'MotifCompendium-Reference'). We then used this 'reference' motif patterns to label the indirect motif-only ENCODE TF MotifCompendium motif patterns, by matching with a

similarity greater than 0.88, Any remaining motif patterns were labeled as 'unknown'. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Example process for collapsing FOX dimer motif, starting from TF ChIP-seq BPNNet-derived motifs into ENCODE TF MotifCompendium pattern. The process was repeated across 19,739 TF ChIP-seq BPNNet-derived motifs, resulting in 1,921 unique motif patterns. (1) Divide motifs per TF, per direct/indirect binding mode (via matching with *in vitro*-confirmed motifs). (2) Cluster unique motifs per TF, per direct/indirect binding mode (indirect binding mode labeled as 'X'). (3) Cluster again, to obtain the final, unique motif pattern.

With the ENCODE TF Motif Compendium, we performed the following preliminary analyses. First, examining the final motif patterns and all their possible direct binding

TFs, we observed that, as anticipated, many binding patterns are shared by more than one TF, often even outside of sequence lineage.

Second, constructing a matrix of major motif pattern by its direct and indirect binding constituent TFs, we observed an initial map of cooperative interaction between TFs, where for a given motif pattern, the direct binding TF(s) are TFs that directly bind with affinity as the motif pattern itself, while the indirect TF(s) are TFs that have also shown to exhibit the same motif pattern in ChIP-seq under *in vivo* conditions, but under *in vitro* conditions, do not exhibit the same motif pattern, suggesting that *in vivo*, the indirect TF potentially binds with the direct TF, resulting in a [direct TF, responsible for the motif]-[indirect, ChIP-target TF]-[antibody] complex. (Figure 4)

Third, in order to understand the motifs in the context of previously known motifs, we compared the final motif patterns to publicly available human TF motif databases: JASPAR 2024 Core, HOCOMOCO V13, and CIS-BP V3, by determining for each database, the proportion of motifs that are explained by ENCODE TF Motif Compendium and vice versa, by finding its closest match while applying an increasing similarity score threshold (from 0.75, 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, to 0.95). We observed that only a limited set of motifs are explained by existing TF motif databases.

Comparing with JASPAR and HOCOMOCO, out of 1,921 ENCODE TF Motif Compendium motif patterns, only 145 (8%) and 217 (11%) motifs match with a similarity greater than 0.9 with JASPAR V2024 Core-HomoSapiens and HOCOMOCO V13-Core motifs respectively, while inversely, 894 (59%) out of the 1,518 JASPAR motifs and 770 (48%) out of the HOCOMOCO 1,611 motifs matched with a similarity greater than 0.9 against the ENCODE TF-MotifCompendium motifs, suggesting that the two databases can only partially describe the ENCODE TF Motif Compendium motifs, while the ENCODE TF Motif Compendium motifs can describe over half of the two databases' motifs. Additionally, there is a relatively high redundancy of motifs in both databases (from a motif pattern point of view) - as expected, as the databases are curated per TF, not per motif pattern type. Extending the comparison to CIS-BP, we see a similar pattern: with only 309 (16%) of ENCODE TF Motif Compendium motifs explained with a similarity greater than 0.9 by CIS-BP V3.0-HomoSapiens motifs, while 3,568 (49%) out of the 7,337 CIS-BP motifs matched to the unified ENCODE motifs. (Figure 6A)

Figure 4. (Below) Matrix of 1,921 ENCODE TF Motif Compendium motif patterns vs. 464 ChIP target TFs, showing direct and indirect binders of each motif pattern (red: direct binding; blue: unvalidated, indirect binding; 1 in 3 TF names shown). TFs and motif patterns sorted by hierarchical clustering, to show similar grouping.

ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium: Consolidated ENCODE DNase-seq and ATAC-seq ChromBPNet-derived motifs

Similar to TF ChIP-seq BPNet-derived motifs, DNase-seq and ATAC-seq ChromBPNet-derived motifs required dataset specific considerations during motif consolidation. First, there is no direct way of identifying the TF responsible for DNase-seq and ATAC-seq motifs. DNase-seq and ATAC-seq map chromatin accessibility broadly, without TF-specific targeting, and without multi-omic gene expression data, we cannot isolate binding to any subset of TFs. In other words, all DNase-seq and ATAC-seq motifs are ‘indirect’. Second, DNase-seq and ATAC-seq are commonly applied to different cell types under different cell states to map accessible euchromatin under the specific cell conditions. However, again, as we used bulk tissue, single omic datasets without gene expression, we had no quantitative measure of cellular context, and could only rely on the natural language annotations of each dataset, making grouping of datasets highly difficult. Additionally, while ENCODE datasets have cell type annotation categories (biosample, cell, organ, developmental state, and system slims), many experiments had missing or multiple cell type annotations, and biosample descriptions were subjective and at varying levels of detail, some with granular description of biomarkers and temporal descriptions while others were simple organ descriptions. We used MotifCompendium to best resolve these issues, while collapsing motifs into a unique, non-redundant set.

First, we selected a common, tissue-level cell type categorization that could be applied across all datasets and assigned each model cell type label. This resulted in grouping the models into 99 cell types with comparable granularity. Then, we filtered out for low complexity motifs, including tandem repeats and GC/AT bias. This resulted in 59,302 initial motifs across the 99 cell type annotations.

Next, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motifs that drive chromatin accessibility in each cell type, we performed a first round of clustering of motifs per cell type. The clustering method was the same as in TF ChIP-seq BPNet motifs. This resulted in 7,749 unique, cell type-specific clusters, across 99 cell types. Again, each cluster was averaged over its constituent motifs to construct a single representative motif per cluster.

Lastly, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motif patterns that are generally observed in DNase-seq and ATAC-seq, agnostic of cell type, (or in other words, all major motif patterns that generally drive chromatin accessibility), we performed a second round of clustering on the 7,749 cell type-specific cluster motifs. The clustering method was again, the same as in the first round. This resulted in 1,762 unique, chromatin accessibility-driving motif patterns in total. We refer to this final set as

'ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium'. Again, in order to identify all possible TFs that could potentially be responsible for the motifs, we used the separately clustered 'MotifCompendium-Reference' that contains 888 unique motif patterns from external motif databases, each with a mapping of its constituent motifs' TFs, and labeled the ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium motif patterns, by matching with a similarity greater than 0.88, Any unmatched motif patterns were labeled as 'unknown'.

With the ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium, we performed the following preliminary analyses. First, constructing a matrix of major motif patterns by the cell types that the motif pattern was found in, we observed an initial map of key motifs and TFs responsible for chromatin accessibility within each cell type. Motifs (and hence TFs), such as CTCF and AP1 family, are responsible for chromatin accessibility across all cell types, while cell type-specific TFs, such as X in Y cell type, were observed to be responsible for accessibility only in their specific cell types. (Figure 5)

Second, in order to understand the motifs in the context of previously known motifs, we again compared the final motif patterns to publicly available human TF motif databases: JASPAR 2024 Core, HOCOMOCO V13, and CIS-BP V3, by determining for each database, the proportion of motifs that are explained by ENCODE Chromatin-MotifCompendium and vice versa, We observed that more motifs are explained by existing databases than ENCODE TF Motif Compendium, however, there are still a significant number of unmatched motifs.

Again, comparing with JASPAR and HOCOMOCO, out of 1,762 ENCODE Chromatin-MotifCompendium motif patterns, only 108 (6%) and 134 (8%) motifs match with a similarity greater than 0.9 when compared to JASPAR V2024 Core-HomoSapiens and HOCOMOCO V13-Core motifs respectively, while inversely, 843 (56%) out of the 1,518 JASPAR motifs and 685 (43%) out of the HOCOMOCO 1,611 motifs matched with a similarity greater than 0.9 against the ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium motifs, suggesting that the two databases can only partially describe the ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium motifs. Extending the comparison to CIS-BP, we again see a similar pattern: with only 213 (12%) of ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium motifs explained with a similarity greater than 0.9 by CIS-BP V3.0-HomoSapiens motifs, while 3,044 (41%) out of the 7,337 CIS-BP motifs matched to the unified ENCODE motifs. (Figure 6B)

Figure 5. Matrix of 1,762 ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium motif patterns vs. 99 Cell type annotations, showing shared and cell type-specific motif patterns observed per cell type. Motif patterns sorted by hierarchical clustering, to show cell type-specific grouping. Cell types sorted by system annotation.

Lastly, in order to understand the difference in motif patterns from ChIP-seq to those from DNase-seq and ATAC-seq, we compared the final motif patterns of ENCODE TF Motif Compendium ('TF motifs') to the final motif patterns of ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium ('chromatin motifs'). We observe that both motif sets are significantly orthogonal to each other, with only 268 (14%) out of 1,921 TF motifs matched with a similarity greater than 0.9 against chromatin motifs, and very closely, 257 (15%) of

1,762 chromatin motifs matched with a similarity greater than 0.9 against TF motifs. The near 1:1 mapping of matched motifs additionally shows that, as expected, each motif set contains no redundant patterns (where one motif from one set would explain more than one motif in another). However, as we decrease the similarity match threshold, the chromatin motifs are explained increasingly more by the TF motifs, with only 216 motifs (12%) left unmatched with a similarity below 0.75. This suggests that many chromatin motifs are related, modified variations of TF motifs, potentially dependent on cell type context. On the other hand, TF motifs maintain a high unexplained fraction, with 541 motifs (28%) unmatched with a similarity below 0.75. This suggests not all TFs are involved in chromatin accessibility, and that DNase-seq and ATAC-seq may not always show the full landscape of TF binding activity. This provides strong evidence that TF ChIP-seq datasets (across many TFs) and chromatin accessibility datasets (across many cell types) provide two orthogonal but complementary lexicons of transcriptional regulation. (Figure 6D)

In order to obtain a final, unique, consolidated set of motif patterns from both ChIP-seq and DNase-seq/ATAC-seq, we combined the ENCODE TF Motif Compendium motif patterns and the ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium motif patterns with the following method. We wanted to keep in mind while combining that new sets of motifs from additional sources (such as transcription initiation-related motifs, from PRO-cap datasets and ProCapNet models³⁶) will need to continue to be added to the regulatory lexicon, and as such, we wanted to maintain flexibility to add such motifs, without having to run the full pipeline from scratch every time. Therefore, here, we did not apply a clustering approach, as clustering algorithms can be non-deterministic and dependent on initial starting constituents. Instead, we performed a similarity comparison between the two sets of motifs, identified all pairs of motifs with a similarity score greater than 0.92, and merged only motifs across sets and only once with the best matching motif, to ensure that motifs within a set were never merged (assuming that the starting motif set was constructed properly and deliberately), and that only one motif from one set would merge with one motif from another set, corresponding to the highest match score. This resulted in a final set of 3,473 motif patterns. And in order to identify all possible TFs that could potentially be responsible for the final motif patterns, we inherited the label of the original motif pattern, either merging the two list of TFs that each set had identified as responsible if both lists were present, inheriting only from one if only one had identified direct binding TFs, or as 'unknown' if neither side was unannotated. We refer to this final set as 'ENCODE Motif Compendium'

Finally, with the combined motif patterns, in order to understand them in the context of previously known motifs one last time, we compared the final motif patterns to publicly available human TF motif databases: JASPAR 2024 Core, HOCOMOCO V13 Core, and

CIS-BP V3. Given that the motifs were simply consolidated from the previously analyzed TF and chromatin motif patterns, with limited overlap, we continued to observe similar findings: existing TF motif databases failed to fully recapitulate ENCODE Motif Compendium motifs, with 723 final motif patterns not matching with any known motif from JASPAR, HOCOMOCO, or CIS-BP with a lenient similarity score, greater than 0.75, while ENCODE Motif Compendium successfully matched a significant fraction of existing motifs: 67% of JASPAR 2024 Core, 54% of HOCOMOCO V13 Core, and 53% of CIS-BP V3 with a similarity score greater than 0.9, that increases to 98% of JASPAR 2024 Core, 92% of HOCOMOCO V13 Core, and 92% of CIS-BP V3 when matching with a more lenient similarity score, greater than 0.75. (Figure 6C)

Figure 6. Comparison of ENCODE Motif Compendium motif patterns vs. External motif databases: JASPAR 2024 Core-*Homo Sapiens*, HOCOMOCO V13 Core, CIS-BP V3-*Homo Sapiens*. Bars show number and fraction of one set of motifs matched when using the other set as a reference, under decreasing similarity score thresholds (more lenient). **A.** ENCODE TF Motif Compendium. **B.** ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium. **C.** Combined ENCODE Motif Compendium. **D.** ENCODE TF Motif Compendium vs. ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium

Discussion

This work contains only a preliminary analysis of the ENCODE deep learning resources. We aim to continue to investigate the resources in the following directions. We identified that out of the unannotated, unknown motifs, many are ZNF-like or multimer composites of two or more TFs. For the ZNFs, we aim to align the discovered motifs with known B1H motifs per zinc finger^{31,32}. For composites, we aim to distinguish between hard spacing syntax (where a fixed spacing between motifs is required for cooperativity) vs. soft spacing syntax (where spacing can be dynamic) by confirming predicted assay readouts of spacing mutations *in silico*^{16,17}. We have also not directly associated motif identity with genomic hit instance locations. We aim to investigate trends in instance locations across motifs. We are excited to see our understanding of the lexicon of transcriptional regulation continue to expand.

Methods

BPNet And ChromBPNet Model Training

Data processing and model training

Uniformly processed *Homo sapiens* TF ChIP-seq, DNase-seq and ATAC-seq datasets were obtained from the ENCODE portal at <https://www.encodeproject.org/>. Base-resolution signal tracks were generated from the 5' ends of mapped reads following the removal of PCR duplicates and low-quality reads.

For the BPNet models, we adapted the BPNet architecture and training procedure from Avsec *et al.*¹⁶ (<https://github.com/kundajelab/bpnet-refactor>). The model accepts a one-hot-encoded 2,114 bp input sequence and predicts strand-specific ChIP-seq signal profiles and total log counts over a central 1,000 bp window. The model predicts the residual signal relative to the control input tracks. The architecture comprises nine dilated convolutional layers with residual connections. Profile predictions are generated via an additional convolutional layer applied to the final dilated output, integrating the control signal profiles. Total counts are predicted by applying global average pooling, followed by a dense layer incorporating control total counts. The model is trained using a joint loss function that combines a single negative log-likelihood loss for the profile logits across both the strand and mean squared error for total counts.

Training data consisted of IDR-thresholded peaks and GC-matched non-peak regions in a 3:1 ratio. Outlier peaks with total signal exceeding 1.2× the total signal of the 99th percentile peak were excluded. Data augmentation included random jittering (up to 128 bp) and reverse-complement transformations. Models were trained using chromosome-based 5-fold cross-validation with no overlap between training, validation, and test sets.

For DNase-seq and ATAC-seq data, we followed the preprocessing steps described in Pampari *et al.*¹⁷. Briefly, we first identified datasets as sequenced in a either paired- or single-ended manner, and downloaded the corresponding “alignments” or “unfiltered alignments” files, respectively. We filtered the “unfiltered alignments” files with samtools view using the same arguments as those used for TF ChIP-seq. We merged all BAM files for a single experiment, and rejected experiments that consisted of a mix of single- and paired-ended alignments. We next prepared BigWig files with the appropriate positive and negative strand shifts for each assay type¹⁷. We defined the set of peak regions for DNase data by calling peaks with macs2, filtering to peaks with an FDR-adjusted p value < 0.05, and then merging with the set of ENCODE ccREs matched to that dataset, if available. For ATAC-seq data, we downloaded the default peakset

from the ENCODE website. We then defined a set of GC-matched non-peak (negative) regions for each fold by sampling from the genome, excluding peaks and blacklisted regions, with a ratio of 2:1 of non-peaks to peaks. We then followed the training procedure described in Pampari et al.¹⁷.

Contribution score and motif discovery

Using the trained models, we calculated the contribution of each base in the peak regions of the dataset to the relative log fold change in predicted read counts relative to respective shuffled GC content-matched sequences using DeepLIFT/DeepSHAP¹⁹. We focused on the contribution score from the predicted read counts due to its straightforward interpretability: the sum of contribution scores of all bases and positions of a peak region is equal to the relative log fold change in predicted read count of the peak region compared to a GC-matched, dinucleotide-shuffled reference region. Using the mean count DeepLIFT/DeepSHAP contribution scores across the five model-folds, we performed motif discovery using TF-MoDISco, identifying contribution weight matrices (CWMs) of length 50 bp (initial core motif length 20 bp, add initial flank 5 bp, add final flank 10 bp), and 110 bp (initial core motif length 30 bp, add initial flank 20 bp, add final flank 20 bp), within a region of width 400 bp from the peak summit, and a maximum seqlet count of 50,000.

Model quality

Using the discovered CWMs, we manually selected models for which a known motif of the CHIP target TF was identified by comparing with publicly available motifs from JASPAR 2024 Core²⁸, HOCOMOCO V13²⁹, CIS-BP V3³⁰, zinc finger bacterial one-hybrid (B1H) system^{31,32}. Except for the ZNF models, which generally result in lower model performance, all models were also filtered for having greater than a median 0.5 Pearson correlation coefficient for the counts head across the model folds. This resulted in a set of 1,644 models that passed initial manual curation. Furthermore, we utilized MotifCompendium to further refine our model selection. To ensure high-quality models capturing TF binding properties, we selected BpNet models that discovered a motif matching a known motif of the CHIP target TF or its paralog in the JASPAR 2024 CORE or JASPAR 2024 UNVALIDATED collections²⁸, with a similarity score greater than 0.88. This resulted in a final set of 1,343 models and 15,615 CWMs across 292 TFs that passed model quality checks.

MotifCompendium

Motif Similarity

We sought to develop a notion of similarity between motifs that enjoys nice mathematical properties and is amenable to GPU acceleration. Our similarity metric is

symmetric; bound between 0 and 1, with a similarity of 1 only being achieved by identical motifs; and can be computed entirely through tensor arithmetic, making it easily parallelizable and GPU accelerate-able.

In this work, motifs are represented as non-negative, Frobenium-norm-normalized matrices with the first dimension being the length of the motif and the second dimension being the genomic bases at each position. We will denote the set of motifs of length L with C “base channels” as $M^{L,C} = \{\|X\|_F = 1\}$.

A challenge when computing similarity between motifs is that the motif itself may only take up a positional sub-window of the motif matrix. For example, a GATA motif of length 5 may be placed in a motif matrix of length 30 such that $X_{10-15,1-C}^{GATA}$ contains the

actual GATA motif, with $X_{1-9,1-C}^{GATA}$ and $X_{16-30,1-C}^{GATA}$ containing unimportant flanking bases.

Because of this, motif matrices must be aligned before a meaningful similarity can be computed. That is to say, if two motif matrices $X^{GATA}, Y^{GATA} \in M^{30,C}$ both contain GATA, but the actual positional sub-windows containing the main motif are $X_{10-15,1-C}^{GATA}$ and $Y_{1-5,1-C}^{GATA}$, it must first be identified that positions 10-15 for motif matrix X^{GATA} correspond to positions 1-5 for motif matrix Y^{GATA} .

In this work, the only alignments that are considered involve positional shifts of the motif matrices with respect to one another optionally combined with reverse complements; we do not consider gapped k-mer alignments. When computing the similarity motif Y has to motif X , motif X will be kept in place and motif Y will be aligned with respect to motif X .

For $X, Y \in M^{L,C}$, there are $2L - 1$ nontrivial positional shifts of motif Y with respect to motif X . We define this set of nontrivial shifts as

$H_L := \{-L + 1, -L + 2, \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots, L - 2, L - 1\} = \{|h| \leq L - 1\}$. When motif Y is shifted by $h \in H_L$, position $Y_{i,1-C}$ becomes aligned with position $X_{i+h,1-C}$. An additional

$2L - 1$ alignments are considered for which the reverse complement of Y is shifted with respect to X instead of Y itself. This leads to a total of $2 \times (2L - 1)$ alignments to consider when comparing two motifs of length L .

We formalize these alignments through the following functional operations. The reverse complement of a motif matrix can be formalized with the function below. In this formalization, the function takes a motif matrix and an indicator variable; if the indicator variable is 1, the reverse complement is performed, otherwise, the matrix is left as is.

$$RC: M^{L,C} \times Z_2 \rightarrow M^{L,C}, RC(X, r) = \{Y \text{ where } Y_{ij} = X_{L+1-i, C+1-j} \text{ if } r = 1, X_{ij} \text{ if } r = 0\}$$

A motif shift is formalized as an expand+shift operation in which a motif matrix of length L is first mapped to a motif matrix of length $3L - 2$ in a 0-padded expansion operation

and then shifted within that $3L - 2$ length context. This operation preserves the norm of the matrix.

$Sh: M^{L,C} \times H_L \rightarrow M^{3L-2,C}$, $Sh(X, h) = Y$ where $Y_{i,j} = \{X_{i-L+1-h,j}, L + h \leq i \leq 2L - 1 + h, 0, \text{ otherwise}$

All possible alignments can then be expressed as a composition of the reverse complement and expand+shift functions.

The similarity between two aligned motifs is computed as a Frobenius inner product between the matrices representing the two motifs. That is, the similarity between motifs

$X, Y \in M^{L,C}$ when Y is optionally reverse complemented with indicator $r \in Z_2$ and then

shifted by $h \in H_L$ is given by the function

$$s: M^{L,C} \times M^{L,C} \times Z_2 \times H_L \rightarrow R, s(X, Y, r, h) = \sum_{i=1}^{3L-2} \sum_{j=1}^C Sh(X, 0)_{i,j} \cdot Sh(RC(Y, r), h)_{i,j}$$

We finally define the similarity of motif Y with respect to motif X as the maximum similarity that X and Y have over all possible alignments.

$$S: M^{L,C} \times M^{L,C} \rightarrow R, S(X, Y) = s(X, Y, r, h)$$

The optimal alignment, r^*, h^* can be computed as

$$r^*(X, Y), h^*(X, Y) = s(X, Y, r, h)$$

Another way of stating this is

$$r^*(X, Y) = \{0, s(X, Y, 0, h) > s(X, Y, 1, h) \text{ 1, otherwise}$$

$$h^*(X, Y) = s(X, Y, r^*(X, Y), h)$$

The similarity function $S(X, Y)$ is symmetric, so the similarity of motif Y with respect to motif X is exactly equal to the similarity of motif X with respect to motif Y . The similarity function is a cosine similarity between vectorized representations of the motifs, thus bounding the similarity to be between $[0, 1]$, with a similarity of 1 achieved if and only if motifs X and Y are identical.

The optimal alignment reverse complement indicator is also symmetric. That is,

$$r^*(X, Y) = r^*(Y, X)$$

However, the optimal alignment shift is symmetric if $r^*(X, Y) = 1$ and skew-symmetric otherwise. That is,

$$h^*(Y, X) = \{-h^*(X, Y), r^*(Y, X) = 0 \text{ } h^*(X, Y), r^*(Y, X) = 1$$

As it stands, this similarity metric is defined for motif matrices of the same length.

However, it can easily be extended to motifs of different lengths. Given $X \in M^{L_1,C}$ and $Y \in M^{L_2,C}$ with $L_1 < L_2$, the length matched motif extension of X can be constructed as

$$\tilde{X} \in M^{L_2 \times C}, \tilde{X}_{i,j} = \{X_{i,j}, 1 \leq i \leq L_1, 0, \text{ otherwise}\}$$

Then, the similarity between X and Y can be computed as the similarity between \tilde{X} and Y .

Numerical algorithm

The following observations about the nature of this similarity calculation motivate our motif similarity algorithm.

First, notice that the similarity between two aligned motifs can be rewritten as a sum over per-base similarity of the aligned motifs.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } s_j(X, Y, r, h) &:= \sum_{i=1}^{3L-2} Sh(X, 0)_{i,j} \cdot Sh(RC(Y, r), h)_{i,j} \\ s(X, Y, r, h) &= \sum_{j=1}^C \left(\sum_{i=1}^{3L-2} Sh(X, 0)_{i,j} \cdot Sh(RC(Y, r), h)_{i,j} \right) = \sum_{j=1}^C s_j(X, Y, r, h) \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $s_j(X, Y, r, h)$ is now simply a dot product between column vectors of $Sh(X, 0)$ and $Sh(RC(Y, r), h)$. In order to compute $S(X, Y)$, we will need to compute this aligned similarity across all shifts. This would be equivalent to computing the $s_j(X, Y, r, h)$ dot product multiple times for each shift. These parallel calculations can be expressed as a single matrix-vector product. Let matrix $U^{(j,r)} \in R^{2L-1 \times 3L-2}$ and vector $v^{(j)} \in R^{3L-2}$ have definitions

$$\begin{aligned} U_{i,j}^{(j,r)} &:= Sh(RC(Y, r), -2L + i)_{j,j} \\ v_i^{(j)} &:= Sh(X, 0)_{i,j} \end{aligned}$$

More simply, $U^{(j,r)}$ is a matrix where each row the j^{th} column vector of $Sh(RC(Y, r), h)$ for each $h \in H_L$. Another way to look at $U^{(j,r)}$ is as a tiling of the j^{th} base channel of $RC(Y, r)$ for every possible shift of Y with respect to X . And $v^{(j)}$ is a vector corresponding to j^{th} base channel of $Sh(X, 0)$, which is just a vector with $X_{\cdot,j}$ at the center.

The resulting product, $w^{(j,r)} := U^{(j,r)} v^{(j)} \in R^{2L-1}$ is a vector where the k^{th} element, $w_k^{(j,r)} = s_j(X, Y, r, -2L + k)$ is the j^{th} base's contribution to the k^{th} shift out of the $2L - 1$ shifts, $(H_L)_k$. It then follows that summing across the bases gives the full similarities. That is,

$$\omega^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^C w^{(j,r)} = \sum_{j=1}^C U^{(j,r)} v^{(j)}$$

Each element of $\omega^{(r)}$ corresponds to the similarity of motifs X and Y in a particular alignment. That is, $\omega_k^{(r)} = s(X, Y, r, -2L + k)$. It then follows that the maximum value across $\omega^{(r)}$ is the highest similarity based on the reverse complement indicator, and the index of the maximum value corresponds to the highest similarity shift.

$$\omega_k^{(r)} = s(X, Y, r, h)$$

$$\omega_k^{(r)} - L = s(X, Y, r, h)$$

Computing both $\omega^{(0)}$ and $\omega^{(1)}$ can be used to compute $S(X, Y)$, $r^*(X, Y)$, and $h^*(X, Y)$.

$$S(X, Y) = \left(\omega_k^{(0)}, \omega_k^{(1)} \right)$$

$$r^*(X, Y) = \begin{cases} 0, & \omega_k^{(0)} > \omega_k^{(1)} \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$h^*(X, Y) = \omega_k^{(r^*(X, Y))} - L$$

These equations are the basis of the algorithm we use to compute this similarity metric.

Algorithm:

- For each base channel, j , create $v^{(j)}$, a vector with the j^{th} column of X at its center
- For r in $[0, 1]$
 - For each base channel, j , create $U^{(j,r)}$, a tiling of the j^{th} column of Y
 - For each base channel, j , compute the matrix-vector product
$$w^{(j,r)} = U^{(j,r)} v^{(j)}$$
 - Sum across all bases $\omega^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^C w^{(j,r)}$
 - Compute the best similarity and alignment for r as $S^{(r)} := \omega_k^{(r)}$, $h^{(r)*} := \omega_k^{(r)}$
- Compute the similarity and optimal alignment as $S(X, Y) = (S^{(0)}, S^{(1)})$,
$$r^* = 0 \text{ if } S^{(0)} > S^{(1)} \text{ else } 1, h^* = \omega_k^{(r^*)}$$

The algorithm above describes the algorithm for computing the similarity between two motif matrices. If we wanted to compute the pairwise similarity between two sets of motifs, we would need to loop through all pairs of motifs and use the above algorithm on each pair. However, the above algorithm can be extended to compute the pairwise similarity of sets of motifs all at once.

Tomtom Similarity Score Benchmark

We first computed the pairwise similarity of all 6,302 motifs in the Human Development Multiomic Atlas²⁵ using MotifCompendium and Tomtom. The Tomtom similarity scores were computed using memsuite-lite²³. For the calculations, `n_target_bins=None` was set to make sure exact scores were being computed. The resulting p-value matrix was clipped so that all values below $1e-16$ were clipped to $1e-16$ (this is because memsuite-lite's implementation occasionally gives negative p-values for what are supposed to be very low p-values); the Tomtom similarity values in Figure 2e are the $-\log_{10}(\text{p-values})$ of similarity.

First, all motif self-similarities were considered. MotifCompendium's self-similarity was always 1 and Tomtom's self-similarity was always $1e-16$.

Then, we considered other motif pairs. First for each MotifCompendium similarity score between 0 and 1 (going in increments of 0.01), we considered all pairs with a similarity threshold of that ± 0.025 (so that all bins would be non-overlapping); then, we found the median Tomtom similarity score in that range. Doing so, we got a median correspondence between MotifCompendium and Tomtom's similarity scores; this is depicted with the gray dashed line in the top left scatterplot of Figure 2e. Then, we considered 4 similarity thresholds - Tomtom's $1e-16$ threshold and MotifCompendium's >0.995 threshold (both corresponding to perfect matches) and MotifCompendium's 0.95 ± 0.025 and Tomtom's 9.85 ± 0.3 . The MotifCompendium 0.95 value was chosen because in practice we found it to be a meaningful threshold for similarity. Tomtom's 9.85 ± 0.3 were chosen because they best correspond to MotifCompendium's 0.95. For each of these similarity thresholds, we considered the slice of motif pairs with that similarity value. Then, we made a histogram of those values. Then, we sorted those values and found visual examples of the 2 lowest similarity scores as per the other threshold. So, for example, in Figure 2e.i (top right), we show all pairs that had a Tomtom similarity of $1e-16$. Many had a similarity of 1 as per MotifCompendium, but some had a similarity score as low as 0.7. The motif pair with the highest similarity and the two with the lowest similarity are depicted for each slice.

This analysis gives a visual understanding of how consistent MotifCompendium's similarity measure is as compared to Tomtom's similarity measure.

In order to further investigate how well the two scores correspond, for a sequence of MotifCompendium similarity thresholds (0.7, 0.75, 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, 0.95), we performed Constant-Potts Leiden clustering at each threshold. And, we performed the exact same clustering procedure on the Tomtom similarity matrix at the corresponding median similarity thresholds (1.68, 2.63, 3.60, 4.55, 6.26, 9.86). Clustering was done by creating

a graph over the motifs where two motifs have an edge if their similarity is greater than or equal to the similarity threshold. The graph has weighted edges with the edge weight being the similarity score. The graph is then clustered using the Leiden algorithm (<https://leidenalg.readthedocs.io/en/stable/reference.html#cpmvertexpartition>). For each clustering across both similarity methods, the ARI and AMI with respect to the ground truth were computed using scikit-learn. They were then plotted in Figure 2g.

ENCODE MotifCompendium

ENCODE TF-MotifCompendium

First, we divided the motifs per target TF (while being agnostic of cell type), and cross-referenced each motif to a set of the target TF's known *in vitro*-derived motifs from publicly available TF motif databases: JASPAR 2024 Core²⁸, HOCOMOCO V13²⁹, CIS-BP V3³⁰, Codebook³³, and CAP-SELEX³⁴. Motifs that matched with a known *in vitro*-confirmed motif with a similarity greater than 0.88 were identified as 'direct', and motifs that did not match were identified as 'indirect'. This ensured that all 'direct' motifs have a known, orthogonally validated motif, derived from an *in vitro* setting (without any other cooperative proteins) and were ensured to be a direct binding mode of the target TF and not of any other cooperative TF. In contrast, 'indirect' motifs were identified from the target TF's ChIP-seq, however, had no orthogonal *in vitro* evidence of binding in this affinity pattern, and hence may or may not be the result of direct binding by the target TF. For indirect motifs, we additionally filtered out for low complexity motifs, including tandem repeats and GC/AT bias. This created a starting set of 2,816 direct motifs and 9,077 indirect motifs, organized per TF.

Next, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motifs that describe each TF's direct and indirect binding modes, we performed a first round of clustering of motifs per TF, per direct/indirect categorization, by applying first, Leiden algorithm³⁰ recursively with a Constant Potts Model metric on the similarity matrix thresholded at 0.88 to converge to a stable, coarse round of clustering, followed by applying a Densely Connected Components algorithm³⁵ on the similarity matrix thresholded at 0.92 to ensure that any clusters, when represented as the average of its constituents, could not create another higher order cluster where all its constituents have a similarity greater than 0.92. This resulted in 755 unique direct binding clusters (labeled as '{TF}__{#}'), and 5,137 unvalidated, indirect binding clusters (labeled as '{TF}_X_{#}') across 464 TFs. Each cluster was averaged over its constituent motifs to construct a single representative motif per cluster.

Lastly, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motif patterns that are generally observable from ChIP-seq, agnostic of target TF (or in other words, all major observable

ChIP-seq motif patterns), we performed a second round of clustering on the 755 direct and 5,137 indirect cluster motifs. The clustering method was the same as in the first round. This resulted in 1,921 unique, general ChIP-seq-derived motif patterns in total. We refer to this final set as the 'ENCODE TF Motif Compendium'. In order to keep track of all possible TFs that could potentially be directly binding to the motifs, we took three approaches to labeling: for the simplest case, where the motif pattern contains one or more direct motifs as its constituents, we labeled the identity of all the direct motif's target TFs as the possible binding TFs of the motif pattern. For motif patterns that do not have any direct motifs as its constituents, we separately clustered known motifs from multiple highly curated, external TF motif databases, whose motif-to-TF mapping was consequently known, into 888 unique motif patterns, and created a mapping of each major motif pattern to all its constituent motifs' TFs (called 'MotifCompendium-Reference'). We then used this 'reference' motif patterns to label the indirect motif-only ENCODE TF MotifCompendium motif patterns, by matching with a similarity greater than 0.88. Any remaining motif patterns were labeled as 'unknown'.

With the ENCODE TF-MotifCompendium, we performed the following preliminary analyses. First, examining the final motif patterns and all their possible direct binding TFs, we observed that, as anticipated, many binding patterns are shared by more than one TF, often even outside of sequence lineage.

Second, constructing a matrix of major motif pattern by its direct and indirect binding constituent TFs, we observed an initial map of cooperative interaction between TFs, where for a given motif pattern, the direct binding TF(s) are TFs that directly bind with affinity as the motif pattern itself, while the indirect TF(s) are TFs that have also shown to exhibit the same motif pattern in ChIP-seq under *in vivo* conditions, but under *in vitro* conditions, do not exhibit the same motif pattern, suggesting that *in vivo*, the indirect TF potentially binds with the direct TF, resulting in an (direct TF, responsible for the motif)-(indirect, ChIP-target TF)-(antibody) complex.

Third, in order to understand the motifs in the context of previously known motifs, we compared the final motif patterns to publicly available human TF motif databases: JASPAR 2024 Core, HOCOMOCO V13, CIS-BP V3, and CAP-SELEX, by determining for each database, the proportion of motifs that are explained by ENCODE TF-MotifCompendium and vice versa, by finding its closest match while applying an increasing similarity score threshold (from 0.75, 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, to 0.95).

ENCODE Chromatin-MotifCompendium

Similar to TF ChIP-seq BPNNet-derived motifs, DNase-seq and ATAC-seq ChromBPNNet-derived motifs required dataset specific considerations during motif

consolidation. First, there is no direct way of identifying the TF responsible for DNase-seq and ATAC-seq motifs. DNase-seq and ATAC-seq map chromatin accessibility broadly, without TF-specific targeting, and without multi-omic gene expression data, we cannot isolate binding to any subset of TFs. In other words, all DNase-seq and ATAC-seq motifs are ‘indirect’. Second, DNase-seq and ATAC-seq are commonly applied to different cell types under different cell states to map accessible euchromatin under the specific cell conditions. However, again, as we used bulk tissue, single omic datasets without gene expression, we had no quantitative measure of cellular context, and could only rely on the natural language annotations of each dataset, making grouping of datasets highly difficult. Additionally, while ENCODE datasets have cell type annotation categories (biosample, cell, organ, developmental state, and system slims), many experiments had missing or multiple cell type annotations, and biosample descriptions were subjective and at varying levels of detail, some with granular description of biomarkers and temporal descriptions while others were simple organ descriptions. We used MotifCompendium to best resolve these issues, while collapsing motifs into a unique, non-redundant set.

First, we selected a common, tissue-level cell type categorization that could be applied across all datasets and assigned each model cell type label. This resulted in grouping the models into 99 cell types with comparable granularity. Then, we filtered out for low complexity motifs, including tandem repeats and GC/AT bias. This resulted in 59,302 initial motifs across the 99 cell type annotations.

Next, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motifs that drive chromatin accessibility in each cell type, we performed a first round of clustering of motifs per cell type. The clustering method was the same as in TF ChIP-seq BPNNet motifs. This resulted in 7,749 unique, cell type-specific clusters, across 99 cell types. Again, each cluster was averaged over its constituent motifs to construct a single representative motif per cluster.

Lastly, in order to identify the non-redundant set of motif patterns that are generally observed in DNase-seq and ATAC-seq, agnostic of cell type, (or in other words, all major motif patterns that generally drive chromatin accessibility), we performed a second round of clustering on the 7,749 cell type-specific cluster motifs. The clustering method was again, the same as in the first round. This resulted in 1,762 unique, chromatin accessibility-driving motif patterns in total. We refer to this final set as ‘ENCODE Chromatin-MotifCompendium’. Again, in order to identify all possible TFs that could potentially be responsible for the motifs, we used the separately clustered ‘MotifCompendium-Reference’ that contains 888 unique motif patterns from external motif databases, each with a mapping of its constituent motifs’ TFs, and labeled the

ENCODE Chromatin-MotifCompendium motif patterns, by matching with a similarity greater than 0.88, Any unmatched motif patterns were labeled as 'unknown'.

With the ENCODE Chromatin-MotifCompendium, we performed the following preliminary analyses. First, constructing a matrix of major motif pattern by the cell types that the motif pattern was found in, we observed an initial map of key motifs and TFs responsible for chromatin accessibility within each cell type. Motifs (and hence TFs), such as CTCF and AP1 family, are responsible for chromatin accessibility across all cell types, while cell type-specific TFs, such as X in Y cell type, were observed to be responsible for accessibility only in their specific cell types.

ENCODE Motif Compendium

In order to obtain a final, unique, consolidated set of motif patterns from both ChIP-seq and DNase-seq/ATAC-seq, we combined the ENCODE TF Motif Compendium motif patterns and the ENCODE Chromatin Motif Compendium motif patterns with the following method. We wanted to keep in mind while combining that new sets of motifs from additional sources (such as transcription initiation-related motifs, from PRO-cap datasets and ProCapNet models) will need to continue to be added to the regulatory lexicon, and as such, we wanted to maintain flexibility to add such motifs, without having to run the full pipeline from scratch every time. Therefore, here, we did not apply a clustering approach, as clustering algorithms can be non-deterministic and dependent on initial starting constituents. Instead, we performed a similarity comparison between the two sets of motifs, identified all pairs of motifs with a similarity score greater than 0.92, and merged only motifs across sets and only once with the best matching motif, to ensure that motifs within a set were never merged (assuming that the starting motif set was constructed properly and deliberately), and that only one motif from one set would merge with one motif from another set, corresponding to the highest match score. This resulted in a final set of 3,473 motif patterns. And in order to identify all possible TFs that could potentially be responsible for the final motif patterns, we inherited the label of the original motif pattern, either merging the two list of TFs that each set had identified as responsible if both lists were present, inheriting only from one if only one had identified direct binding TFs, or as 'unknown' if neither side was unannotated. We refer to this final set as 'ENCODE Motif Compendium'.

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